

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Project "SIMPLE"

Deliverable D4.3

**EU scale simulation of reduced fertilization
scenarios**

Due date of deliverable: M57
Actual submission date: 12.11.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title:

Project website:

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D4.3
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	EU scale simulation of reduced fertilization scenarios
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP4
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Soil organic carbon
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Rene Dechow, Thuenen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture
AUTHOR:	Benjamin Pape
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14069147
LICENSE	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

ABSTRACT

Soil organic carbon is an effective measure to remove and store CO₂ and is one of the few available large-scale CO₂ sinks that could help mitigate climate change. The amount of soil organic carbon (SOC) is a balance of the carbon input from plants and organic amendments and the carbon output due to mineralisation. A reduction in N fertilisation, as proposed by the F2F strategy, decreases the plant growth which leads to lower C input in form of above- and belowground harvest residues. Based on estimated yield reductions from WP3 from -20% mineral N fertilisation, we derived the corresponding loss in carbon input and its impact on soil organic carbon after 30 years. European scale simulations were performed for the six major crops wheat, barley, maize, rapeseed, potatoes and sugar beet. Given the lack of data on how/if plant carbon allocation changes under nitrogen reduction, two common allocation functions were applied, each of them coupled to a version of the widely applied soil organic carbon model RothC that has been calibrated with the respective allocation function. The 20% reduction of mineral nitrogen results in mean European SOC losses of 0.9 t per hectare of agricultural land, mainly caused by wheat and rapeseed cultivation due to the big share in agricultural area and high yield reductions, respectively. Czechia (-2.2 t SOC/ha), United Kingdom (-1.7 t SOC/ha) and Slovakia (-1.6 t SOC/ha) suffer the major losses, due to large shares of high-yielding crop in their agricultural areas. The SOC simulations reveal an overall moderate impact of Farm-to-Fork nitrogen reductions on European SOC due to the six major crops. However, in some countries, these crops cover less than 20% of total agricultural land and, therefore, the real impact in these regions will be -much- higher than our results show.

Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	5
List of Figures.....	5
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Methods.....	6
2.1 Carbon input estimation.....	6
2.2 European scale SOC simulation.....	8
3. Results.....	10
3.1. European scale SOC losses.....	10
3.2. Driver analysis.....	12
4. Discussion.....	15
5. Conclusion.....	16
References.....	17

List of Tables

TABLE 1: Driver analysis of national SOC loss	14
---	----

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: SOC loss total of all crops	10
FIGURE 2: SOC loss of the six crops	11
FIGURE 3: PCA driver analysis	12

List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon

1. Introduction

Soil organic carbon is an effective measure to remove and store CO₂ and is one of the few available large-scale CO₂ sinks that could help mitigate climate change. The amount of soil organic carbon (SOC) is a balance of the carbon input from plants and organic amendments and the carbon output due to mineralisation. The Farm-to-Fork strategy of the European Union proposes the introduction of nitrogen thresholds, more specifically a 20% reduction of nitrogen fertilisation. A reduction in N fertilisation decreases the plant growth which leads to lower C input in form of above- and belowground harvest residues. Thus, SOC stocks are out of balance and will decrease for a longer time until the decreasing carbon loss is in balance with the reduced C input. We estimate the amount of SOC loss after 30 years on European scale with two calibrated versions of the SOC model RothC (Coleman&Jenkinson1996, Dechow2019). We show the average losses of SOC per hectare agricultural area for Europe for the six major crops wheat, maize, barley, rapeseed, potatoes and sugar beet and analyse what drives the SOC loss in the respective country compared to European average. We assume that the reduction in nitrogen fertiliser is fully realised by mineral nitrogen and, thus, that C input from organic amendments stays the same.

2. Methods

2.1. Carbon input estimation

To derive the difference in carbon input, aboveground and belowground, it was decided not to use the data that were sampled in WP4.1 on sites with mean N reductions of about 17%.

Although these data are interesting because they were taken from high-fertilised sites and are therefore particularly suitable for representing the biomass losses that occur on the high-fertilised cropland targeted by the F2F strategy. But, first, for this sampling data aboveground harvest residues are not available. Second, the data were sampled in Germany and in one year only and, thus, can be assumed to be mainly driven by the local weather in this one year and local soil conditions.

A literature review showed that there were very few biomass sampling campaigns that investigated nitrogen reduction of explicitly 20% N based on high fertilisation (WP4.1). The available data shows a wide range of root biomass change due to N reduction, from biomass loss to gain. At first sight, it seems that, just as any other part of the plant, root mass is a) positively correlated to nitrogen fertilisation and b) this only if nitrogen is the limiting factor (see Campbell&Jong2000). For rhizodeposition, Hirte et al. (2018) found no dependence on fertilisation but cite several publications who did observe a positive correlation between rhizodeposition and fertilisation. However, Hirte et al. (2018) and further cited publications found that total belowground carbon input of is independent of fertilisation. For aboveground harvest residues, some literature generally showed straw biomass decreasing linearly with yield and the same when this is due to N fertilisation (Xue2014, Hirte2018, Poeplau2016). In conclusion, literature shows that the response of plant C allocation to N reduction is either not consistent or not apparent and, therefore, we decided to estimate the carbon input with two common allocation functions (AF; Franko2011, Bolinder2007), assuming that a reduction of 20% N does not additionally change the allocation. In Franko's and Bolinder's allocation functions, harvest residues and roots decrease with yield. In addition, the two functions were derived from a) crops that were not highly fertilised and b) some trials varied the nitrogen treatment (see Bolinder2007). Thus, the functions are based on biomass that, at least to a certain degree, was nitrogen limited and, in this way, a possible change in allocation due to nitrogen reduction is

partly included already. It is assumed that absolute straw removal (usually required for animal bedding in Europe) remains unchanged in the F2F scenario while the straw fraction that remains on the field is decreased due to the lower above ground biomass.

Carbon input calculation with Bolinder's allocation function

Martin Bolinder presented a method to estimate carbon input from constant ratios of the four plant parts yield, straw, roots and rhizodeposition. His data is based on 168 treatments from Canada and the U.S. that were taken about 20 to 40 years ago. Carbon input from harvest residues (straw + stubble & "debris") and root is derived from the yield and the constant allocation coefficients C_{hr} , C_{roots} and $C_{exudates}$:

$$C_{in_hr} = \left(\frac{Yield}{C_p} \right) \times C_{hr} \times C_{content} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{in_roots} = \left(\frac{Yield}{C_p} \right) \times (C_{roots} + C_{exudates}) \times C_{content} \quad (2)$$

Many common allocation functions assume a constant allocation of the plant's parts (Taghizadeh-Toosi2014, Jacobs2020, Keel2017), although it is well known that only a part of straw and especially root biomass is explained by yield, i.e. straw and roots are linearly related to yield but not proportionally. The reason for this may be that linear relationships are rarely statistically significant as the very diverse biomass sampling conditions, especially the weather, cause a high variance. The result of the assumption of a constant allocation will always be an underestimation of straw and root C input for low yields and an overestimation for high yields.

Carbon input calculation with Franko's allocation function

Franko assumes a proportional relationship between yield and straw but a non-proportional relationship between roots and yield. Straw is derived from a constant harvest index (HI) :

$$C_{in_straw} = Yield \times HI \times DM_{straw} \times C_{content_straw} \quad (3)$$

with DM_{straw} the dry mass and $C_{content_straw}$ the carbon content of the straw. For the total aboveground harvest residue carbon, the stubble, chaff and short straw that is lost at harvest (from here on summarised as "stubble") $C_{hr-straw}$ are added

$$C_{in_hr} = C_{straw} + C_{hr-straw} \quad (4)$$

Together with root carbon they are part of the "harvest and root residues" C_{in_res}

$$C_{in_res} = (F_{res} \times Yield \times N_{content} + K_{res}) \times CN_{ratio} \quad (5)$$

and, in this way, a part of the aboveground harvest residues in Franko's allocation function is as well non-proportional. To separate the root from the stubble carbon, the root-stubble ratio from the Bolinder equation can be applied, assuming that the ratios are the same in both datasets

$$rootShare_{BOL} = \frac{roots}{(roots + stubble + chaff + short\ straw)} = \frac{C_r \times rootCorr}{(C_r \times rootCorr + C_s \times stubbleFract)} \quad (6)$$

The amount of root carbon then results from

$$C_{roots} = C_{in_res} \times rootShare_{BOL} \quad (7)$$

And the total aboveground C input

$$C_{in_hr} = C_{straw} + C_{hr-straw} = C_{straw} + C_{in_hr} - C_{roots} \quad (8)$$

All parameter values are available in the publication.

The allocation function from Franko is based on 391 treatments from 40 mostly German long-term experiments from about 35 years ago.

2.2 European scale SOC simulation

The SOC loss that results from lower carbon input is estimated with the soil organic carbon model RothC (Coleman&Jenkinson1996). We apply modified DPM/RPM ratios that have been calibrated on 439 SOC data series from 36 arable long-term field experiments in Central and Northern Europe (Dechow2019). Only topsoil (0-30 cm) is considered.

The simulations are run across all countries of Europe + Türkiye on a 10 km grid. The following input data is applied:

1. Crop yield and harvested area (Grogan2022): Based on GAEZ data from 2010, yields and harvested areas are updated to 2015 considering national crop yield and area changes. Regional changes within countries are not taken into account but crop yield and area in each grid cell is adjusted with the same national factor. Based on GAEZ2010 area data, GAEZ2015 crop area data deviates from FAO 2015 data (Germany +13% area; France: -13%; Hungary: -7%, Poland: -4%). For maize, grain maize is reported separately and silage maize is included in an aggregation of fodder crops. Due to the large share of silage maize in European maize cultivation, separate silage maize maps were needed. It is derived based on the maize map and Eurostat data on grain and silage maize for the same years as the GAEZ2015 maps (average 2014-2016). We could only derive silage maize if the respective country cultivates grain maize. Therefore, we could not take into account silage maize production in Estonia (2% of total harvested area), Ireland (5%), Latvia (2%), Sweden (2%) and United Kingdom (6%). Additional deviations are due to the short period of 2014-2016 that is taken into account for GAEZ2015 crop yield and area data. It leads to deviations from the 2012-22 means (Eurostat) of crop area (potatoes: -6.8%; rapeseed: +4.7%; barley: -3%; sugar beet: -2.9%; Eurostat, own calculation) and crop yield (rapeseed: -5.4%; potatoes: +2.2%).
2. Climate data (Pariße2023): Temperature, precipitation and potential evapotranspiration data derived for RothC simulations in EJP SOIL CarboSeq project from the AgERA5 dataset.
3. Soil cover: NDVI-derived mean bare soil probability as in GSOCseq (FAO2020, Chapter 6.4).
4. Clay: OpenLandMap (Hengl2018)
5. Yield N response (WP3) as relative reduction for each of the six crops.

These data are converted and aggregated to the same grid and resolution used by CarboSeq, which is the European Lambert Azimuthal Equal-Area projection (EPSG:3035) and a 10 km grid. In this way, the resulting maps are easy to compare between the projects.

To simulate absolute soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks, carbon input data at European scale is needed from all C sources as organic amendments, cover crops and residue management. The

challenge is that this data, at least at European scale, is not available or in coarse resolution, i.e. needs to be estimated. Thus, absolute stocks might be a very coarse or even a wrong estimation that might rather confuse than help? We therefore do not simulate full organic carbon stocks but only simulate the difference in SOC that is given by lower carbon input under reduced N fertilisation. This is possible because in RothC, as in many models, the decomposition rate in RothC follows first order kinetics, i.e. the rate is linearly related to SOC. This allows to do a simulation considering the difference in carbon input only:

$$C_{in_DIFF_roots} = C_{in_80\%_roots} - C_{in_100\%N_roots} \quad (9)$$

$$C_{in_DIFF_hr} = C_{in_80\%N_hr} - C_{in_100\%N_hr} \quad (10)$$

This results in the SOC difference between two scenarios. Hence, our results show how much SOC we lose when the F2F initiative for nitrogen reduction will be approved and applied.

The resulting SOC differences across Europe can be understood as follows: The SOC difference is a function of C input difference and local mineralisation conditions. Local mineralisation conditions can be quantified with the humification coefficient, which is the ratio of SOC that built up after 30 years and the amount of carbon input over this time (ranges between 10-15%). It depends on the conditions for mineralisation and decreases with temperature, precipitation and lower clay contents. The C input difference is proportionally related to the crop's share in agricultural area and proportionally (Bolinder) or linearly (Franko) related to yield and yield reduction (in %) due to -20% N:

$$SOC_{DIFF_BOLINDER} \propto \text{Yield} \times \text{YieldReduction} \times \text{AreaShare} \times \text{HumificationCoefficient}_{BOLINDER}$$

$$SOC_{DIFF_FRANKO} \sim f_{linear}(\text{Yield}, \text{YieldReduction}) \times f_{proportional}(\text{AreaShare}, \text{Hum. Coefficient}_{FRANKO})$$

The humification coefficient differs between the two applied allocation functions due to the different decomposition rates that are the result of the model calibrations.

3. Results

The following maps consider European SOC losses as the mean value of two SOC simulations using the allometric function of Franko et al (2012) and Bolinder et al (2007) and per hectare of agricultural land of a country (unit t SOC/ha). This unit answers the question: How much SOC does the average agricultural area hectare in country X lose due to -20% N fertilisation of crop Y? The SOC loss per hectare is a measure of soil degradation, as SOC provides soil fertility by e.g. enhanced rootability and water retention.

3.1 European scale SOC losses

Based on the above-mentioned drivers of SOC losses and their spatial distribution, we estimated the effect of a reduction in nitrogen fertilisation (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 1: Total soil organic carbon loss after 30 years from all six SIMPLE crops when -20% N is applied. The unit is SOC loss in tonnes per average hectare of agricultural land in the 10 km grid cell, which is a measure of soil degradation. Hence, the actual size of agricultural land in the grid cell is not taken into account but only the loss of the average hectare, be it one hectare in that grid cell or 10,000. The loss is a function of yield level, yield reduction, share of agricultural land where the crop is grown and the humification coefficient.

Average SOC loss per ha agricultural land on country level: For the six crops simulated (see Fig. 1), Czechia loses most SOC per ha of agricultural land (2.16 t SOC/ha), mainly driven by wheat (0.84 t SOC/ha; 30% of agric. area) and rapeseed (1 t SOC/ha; 15%). Followed by the United Kingdom (1.7

t SOC/ha), Slovakia (1.6 t SOC/ha), France (1.51 t SOC/ha) and Hungary (1.47 t SOC/ha), of which all are driven by wheat and rapeseed SOC losses and Hungary additionally by its larger area share of high-yielding grain maize.

FIGURE 2: Soil organic carbon loss after 30 years from each of the six SIMPLE crops when -20% N is applied. The unit is SOC loss in tonnes hectare of agricultural land in the 10 km grid cell. Hence, the actual size of agricultural land in the grid cell is not taken into account but only the loss of the average hectare, be it one hectare in that grid cell or 10,000. The loss is a function of yield level, yield reduction, share of agricultural land where the crop is grown and the humification coefficient. Maize includes grain and silage maize.

Considering the SOC losses per country split up into the contributions from the six crops (see Fig. 2), Czechia is as well the country where the highest SOC losses for wheat (0.84 t SOC/ha) and rapeseed (1 t SOC/ha) can be found. Due to the enormous share of grain maize of the Serbian agricultural land, the highest SOC loss of grain maize can be found in this country (0.872 t SOC/ha). Silage maize leads to the highest loss in Belgium (0.171 t SOC/ha) and the highest loss due to barley cultivation can be found in Ireland (0.721 t SOC/ha). The cultivation areas for potato and sugar beet are smaller and, by far, largest in the Netherlands (maximum SOC loss of potato: 0.041 t SOC/ha) and Belgium (max. SOC loss of sugar beet: 0.137 t SOC/ha)

Average SOC loss for European agricultural area: On average, European agricultural land loses almost 1 t SOC/ha after 30 years (0.928 t SOC/ha) due to reduced fertilisation. Most of this comes from wheat with 0.353 t SOC/ha, which is mainly due to high wheat harvest residue and root biomass and the high share of total agricultural area that wheat has, followed by rapeseed with a mean SOC loss of 0.220 t SOC/ha that is the result of enormous yield reductions of 20% on average across all European countries. Third comes maize with 0.207 t SOC/ha (grain maize: 0.177 t SOC/ha; silage maize: 0.030 t SOC/ha). Grain maize leaves more biomass on the field than wheat and, therefore, yield reductions lead to even higher SOC losses, but its cultivation area is much smaller. Silage maize shows smaller reductions mainly due to full removal of aboveground harvest

residues, leaving only the root C input difference. Barley is responsible for a loss of 0.117 t SOC/ha, Potatoes 0.007 t SOC/ha and sugar beet for 0.024 t SOC/ha.

SOC loss drivers: Besides the amount of SOC decrease in European countries, most interesting is what it is driven by. The drivers responsible for the average soil organic carbon loss per hectare agricultural land are the yield, the area share of the six crops in total agricultural area, the local humification coefficient (HumCoeff) and the yield reduction (in %; WP3). The driver analysis is based on the SOC simulations performed with the model combining allometric functions after Bolinder et al. (2007) and RothC.

3.2 Driver analysis

The drivers of soil organic carbon losses are visualized in figure 3 by an analysis of their principal components (the four driver values for each country are shown in table 1 further below).

FIGURE 3: Principal Component Analysis of European countries’ SOC losses after 30 years. The unit vectors of the drivers indicate their importance for the countries (HC=HumCoeff; YR=Yield reduction). The relevance of a driver for a country’s average hectare SOC loss is highest when the country is in line with the driver’s arrow direction and in distance from the zero point (e.g. yield and/or area share are important drivers for UK’s SOC). And the other way around, e.g. Portugal’s SOC loss is very little affected by all four drivers compared to European average, it is far from the zero point and against the arrows’ direction. Three “clusters” of countries that are quantitatively more affected by the Farm-to-Fork nitrogen

reductions are marked in the diagram: Drivers are a) elevated yield (closed ellipse), b) elevated crop yield & area (triangle) and c) elevated humification coefficient and yield reduction (dotted ellipse) (see table 1 for driver values).

The principal component analysis reveals three “clusters” of countries that indicate the primary source(s) of SOC loss for the countries belonging to the cluster. The three clusters are a) elevated crop yield, b) elevated crop yield and area (triangle) and c) elevated humification coefficient and yield reduction (dotted ellipse). The correlation between yield and area share is with 0.27 rather moderate and quite high for the humification coefficient and yield reduction ($r=0.79$), as can be observed in figure 3.

Table 1 provides the four driver values for each country that were used for the PCA. It is important to mention that the national driver values are the SOC loss weighted national variable means. Therefore, they do not represent the national variable mean that is derived by averaging over all grid cells of the country, but they are the average over all grid cells where SOC loss occurs. Comparing these mean values with the European average indicates whether it is a relevant driver for SOC loss or not, compared to other European countries (colours red – green). In addition, row-wise driver’s ranking explains their importance for the country’s SOC loss (arrows next to the ratios: green=most important national driver, yellow=medium importance, red=low importance). After bringing all six crops’ driver values together to one national driver value, they have been normalized to one so that e.g. 1.2 stands for 20% above European average. However, this changes the driver’s relation to one another within a country. Thus for national comparison, the national drivers have not been normalized and, therefore, the arrows direction can differ from the normalized ratios.

Example Spain: Compared to the European average, the humification coefficient is 15% lower, however, compared to the other three drivers, it has moderate relevance for SOC decline in Spain. Values at the bottom of the table are the means (1.00, as they have been normalized) and the standard deviations, indicating high variance between the European countries for area share (31%) and yield (28%) and lower variance due to the yield reduction (18%) and humification coefficient (16%).

Country	Yield	Area share	HumCoeff	Yield Reduction
Albania	0,94 →	0,52 ↓	0,91 →	1,05 ↑
Austria	1,34 ↑	0,87 ↓	1,08 ↓	1,07 ↓
Belarus	0,72 ↓	0,62 ↓	1,20 ↑	1,24 ↑
Belgium	1,45 ↑	1,04 →	0,96 ↓	1,12 ↓
Bosnia and Herzegovina	0,59 ↓	1,17 ↑	0,89 ↓	1,07 →
Bulgaria	0,98 →	1,11 ↑	1,19 ↓	1,12 ↓
Croatia	1,03 ↑	1,15 ↑	1,08 ↓	1,22 →
Czechia	1,37 ↑	1,61 ↑	1,16 ↓	1,17 ↓
Denmark	1,44 ↑	1,20 →	1,00 ↓	0,82 ↓
Estonia	0,71 ↓	1,09 ↑	1,03 ↓	1,00 →
Finland	0,65 ↓	1,26 ↑	0,84 ↓	0,84 ↓
France	1,32 ↑	1,32 ↑	1,10 ↓	1,02 ↓
Germany	1,44 ↑	0,98 ↓	1,05 ↓	0,96 ↓
Greece	0,93 ↑	0,54 ↓	0,90 ↑	0,80 →
Hungary	1,12 ↑	1,14 ↑	1,22 ↓	1,22 ↓
Ireland	1,42 ↑	1,53 ↑	0,69 ↓	0,65 ↓
Italy	1,09 ↑	0,79 →	0,84 ↓	0,80 ↓
Latvia	0,86 ↓	0,81 →	1,06 →	1,06 ↑
Lithuania	0,94 →	1,07 ↑	1,10 ↓	1,11 ↓
Luxembourg	1,18 ↑	0,65 ↓	1,11 →	0,91 ↓
Malta	0,83 →	0,49 ↓	0,77 ↑	0,76 ↑
Moldova	0,56 ↓	1,00 ↑	1,23 ↑	1,09 ↑
Montenegro	0,55 ↓	1,30 ↑	0,74 ↓	0,89 ↓
Netherlands	1,22 ↑	0,92 ↑	0,78 ↓	0,82 ↓
North Macedonia	0,75 ↓	0,68 ↓	1,14 ↑	1,15 ↑
Norway	0,86 →	0,90 ↑	0,68 ↓	0,80 ↓
Poland	0,99 ↑	1,03 ↑	1,12 ↓	1,24 ↑
Portugal	0,66 ↓	0,25 ↓	0,75 ↑	0,52 →
Romania	0,75 ↓	1,15 ↑	1,11 ↓	1,05 ↓
Serbia	0,82 ↓	1,54 ↑	1,01 ↓	1,13 ↓
Slovakia	1,19 ↑	1,28 ↑	1,21 ↓	1,13 ↓
Slovenia	1,19 ↑	0,83 ↓	1,03 ↓	1,17 →
Spain	0,71 ↓	0,81 ↑	0,85 →	0,85 →
Sweden	1,13 ↑	0,93 ↑	0,98 ↓	0,88 ↓
Switzerland	1,30 ↑	0,88 ↓	1,01 ↓	1,19 →
Turkey	0,72 ↓	1,14 ↑	0,95 ↓	1,00 ↓
Ukraine	0,86 ↓	0,94 ↑	1,20 ↑	1,16 ↑
United Kingdom	1,42 ↑	1,45 ↑	1,03 ↓	0,92 ↓
	1.00 ± 0.28	1.00 ± 0.31	1.00 ± 0.16	1.00 ± 0.18

TABLE 1: Driver analysis of national SOC loss: The four drivers responsible for the national SOC loss relative to their mean contribution in European countries. Yield, share of the six crops in the country's agricultural land (Area share) and the humification coefficient (HumCoeff) are SOC loss weighted national means and the yield reduction as provided by WP3. The ratios shown are then derived by dividing the national driver mean by the European country mean. Values indicate higher (green) or lower (red) relevance of the respective driver compared to the other European countries (country comparison). **The arrows** are for row-wise comparison of the driver's relevance for the country's SOC loss and can differ from the ratio value next to them (see text for explanation). Example how to read the table: Compared to the other European countries, the six crops' area share in total Norwegian agricultural land is below average. However, row-wise comparison with the other three drivers indicates that area share is the dominant driver of Norway's losses of soil organic carbon. The numbers at the bottom are the mean ± Stdev. The driver analysis is based on the SOC simulations performed with the model environment combining allometric functions after Bolinder et al. (2007) and RothC.

4. Discussion

Soil organic carbon has an important function for soil health and fertility and, thus, any loss will affect agricultural production. The average SOC loss of the European countries due a reduction in fertiliser of 20% is 0.9 t/ha after 30 years. Considered that the average European SOC stock is about 75 t/ha (FAO2022; derived from map as agricultural area-weighted average), this is a rather moderate loss of 1,3% or 33 kg/ha/y. However, figure 1 shows that the loss is very unequally distributed across the countries, following the patterns of the driving factors yield, area share, humification coefficient and yield reduction. The relevance of the area share (CV: 31%, table 1) and yield (28%) for the variations of SOC loss across the continent is well illustrated with the map in figure 1. Agricultural soils in the United Kingdom, France, Czechia, Hungary and Slovakia suffer most from a nitrogen reduction. The origin of the loss, however, is diverse. If and to which extent of total agricultural area the six crops are grown in a country plays a major role. Figure 2 shows the outcome of the nitrogen reduction after 30 years split up into the six crops (maize includes grain and silage maize) and compares well the importance of each of the six crops for European and national soil organic carbon stocks. It indicates that SOC in Czechia as well as France, Hungary and the UK is highly affected by lowered C input from wheat and rapeseed. Extensive maize production in Hungary, Romania, Serbia, Croatia and Slovenia plays the major role in these countries' losses of soil organic carbon. However, as the SOC loss per agricultural hectare is driven by four factors, it is not clear which of the factors are major and minor contributors. As the six crops only cover part of the countries' total agricultural land and, the full impact will be higher than what we derived. Especially in the northern countries Norway, Sweden, Finland as well as in Portugal, we take into account around 20% of total agricultural land only.

The drivers of SOC loss explain why the mentioned countries lose more or less soil organic carbon and an analysis of their contributions provides a more structured understanding of the impact of F2F nitrogen reduction on European soil organic carbon stocks. Table 1 compares the importance of the four drivers with the European average and in this way allows to derive what a country's SOC loss is driven by, compared to European mean. The arrows next to the ratios show the importance of the driver compared to the other three drivers in a country. The numbers in table 1 serve more as a reference for the principal component analysis that was conducted based on these data and is presented in figure 3. Three groups of countries can be identified as being more vulnerable to nitrogen reductions for the six crops: a) elevated crop yield & area (triangle), b) elevated crop yield only (closed ellipse) and c) an elevated humification coefficient (dotted ellipse). It is to be expected that high yields lead to high losses as carbon input increases proportionally/linearly with yield. The high yields can be found in countries with agricultural favourable climates (Ireland, UK, Netherlands, Belgium, France, Germany) and in countries with high N availability due to high density of animal husbandry (Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, Germany). Due to the shape of the yield N response curve do high-fertilised yields lose relatively less yield and hence carbon input. Crop area and yield do not always correlate in regions of high SOC losses but only show a correlation of 0.27 across European countries. Especially Czechia, France and the United Kingdom are vulnerable to SOC losses from the six crops as they have both elevated crop yields and area (see table 1). A third "cluster" is the effect of yield reduction and the humification coefficient. The latter indicates the amount of soil organic carbon that is derived from carbon input, the higher it is the more will the SOC increase and decrease when carbon input changes. The countries affected are Hungary, Belarus, Ukraine, Poland, Moldova, Bulgaria, Croatia and North Macedonia. HumCoeff and yield reduction from WP3 are highly correlated ($r=0.79$), which means that the two effects come together and reinforce the effect of the nitrogen reduction in these countries/regions. The reason for the correlation might be that both decrease with site precipitation and temperature. The humification

coefficient because this increases decomposition, the yield reduction because this will increase yield which means a lower slope of the yield N response curve and in turn a lower yield reduction.

Additional effects of nitrogen reduction on SOC: Yield reduction was considered to be achieved by a reduction in mineral fertiliser only. Thus, no changes in C input due to lower organic amendment applications were taken into account. As well not considered is the additional SOC stock decline due to lower N surplus which increases the C/N ratio. A higher C/N ratio decreases carbon use efficiency and in turn the humification coefficient. The changing C/N ratio of plants with fertilisation would need to be used for the carbon content in C input calculation as well.

5. Conclusion

An overall moderate impact of mineral nitrogen reduction on European soil organic carbon is to be expected from the six crops wheat, maize, barley, rapeseed, potatoes and sugar beet. The losses are driven by the high-yielding and widespread crops wheat, maize and rapeseed in countries with good growing and/or humification conditions. The perfect examples are Czechia and France. The negative trade-off between high-fertilisation and yield reduction and the reinforced SOC loss due to correlation between yield reduction and the humification coefficient exert a smoothening effect on European range of SOC losses. Absolute SOC results should be handled with caution due to uncertainties regarding the input data and the capability of the SOC models. In addition, only part of the agricultural land was simulated which underestimates the impact of F2F for some countries massively. A nitrogen reduction of 20% will have overall moderate effects on European agricultural land. However, regions with favourable growing conditions will suffer more SOC loss than regions with less favourable growing conditions.

References

- Bolinder, M. A., Janzen, H. H., Gregorich, E. G., Angers, D. A., & VandenBygaart, A. J.** (2007). An approach for estimating net primary productivity and annual carbon inputs to soil for common agricultural crops in Canada. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 118(1–4), 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2006.05.013>
- Campbell, C. A., & de Jong, R.** (2001). Root-to-straw ratios—Influence of moisture and rate of N fertiliser. *Canadian Journal of Soil Science*, 81(1), 39–43. <https://doi.org/10.4141/S00-027>
- Coleman, K., Jenkinson, D.**, 1996. RothC-26.3 - A Model for the turnover of carbon in soil, in: Evaluation of Soil Organic Matter Models Using Existing, Long-Term Datasets. pp. 237–246. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-61094-3_17
- Dechow, R., Franko, U., Kätterer, T., & Kolbe, H.** (2019). Evaluation of the RothC model as a prognostic tool for the prediction of SOC trends in response to management practices on arable land. *Geoderma*, 337, 463–478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.10.001>
- Eurostat.** (n.d.). Agricultural production – crops. Eurostat. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics>
- FAO. 2022.** *Global Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Potential Map – SOCseq v.1.1. Technical report*. Rome.
- FAO. 2020.** GSOCseq Global Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Potential Map Technical Manual. G. Peralta, L. Di Paolo, C. Omuto, K. Viatkin, I. Luotto, Y. Yigini, 1st Edition, Rome.
- Franko, U., Kolbe, H., Thiel, E., & Ließ, E.** (2011). Multi-site validation of a soil organic matter model for arable fields based on generally available input data. *Geoderma*, 166(1), 119–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2011.07.019>
- Grogan, D., Frohling, S., Wissler, D., Prusevich, A., & Glidden, S.** (2022). Global gridded crop harvested area, production, yield, and monthly physical area data circa 2015. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01115-2>
- Hengl, T.**, 2018. Clay content in % (kg / kg) at 6 standard depths (0, 10, 30, 60, 100 and 200 cm) at 250 m resolution. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2525663>
- Hirte, J., Leifeld, J., Abiven, S., Oberholzer, H.-R., & Mayer, J.** (2018). Below ground carbon inputs to soil via root biomass and rhizodeposition of field-grown maize and wheat at harvest are independent of net primary productivity. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 265, 556–566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.07.010>
- Jacobs, A., Poeplau, C., Weiser, C., Fahrion-Nitschke, A., & Don, A.** (2020). Exports and inputs of organic carbon on agricultural soils in Germany. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, 118(3), 249–271. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-020-10087-5>
- Keel, S. G., Leifeld, J., Mayer, J., Taghizadeh-Toosi, A., & Olesen, J. E.** (2017). Large uncertainty in soil carbon modelling related to method of calculation of plant carbon input in agricultural systems. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 68(6), 953–963. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12454>
- Parisse, B., Alilla, R., & De Natale, F.** (2023). *EJPSOIL CarboSeq agrometeorological datasets*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399180>
- Taghizadeh-Toosi, A., Christensen, B. T., Hutchings, N. J., Vejlin, J., Kätterer, T., Glendinning, M., & Olesen, J. E.** (2014). C-TOOL: A simple model for simulating whole-profile carbon storage in temperate agricultural soils. *Ecological Modelling*, 292, 11–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2014.08.016>
- Xue, Y.-F., Zhang, W., Liu, D.-Y., Yue, S.-C., Cui, Z.-L., Chen, X.-P., & Zou, C.-Q.** (2014). Effects of nitrogen management on root morphology and zinc translocation from root to shoot of winter wheat in the field. *Field Crops Research*, 161, 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2014.01.009>

